

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

STRATEGIES FOR PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH “PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING” IN SECONDARY SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article explores the effectiveness of Problem-based learning in enhancing critical thinking skills among secondary school education students. By analyzing various studies and integrating practical examples from both local and international contexts, the article demonstrates how PBL fosters student engagement, collaboration, and self-directed learning. PBL allows students to solve real-life problems, promoting the development of critical thinking, language skills, and overall academic performance. The survey findings show that PBL significantly improves students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and apply knowledge in diverse situations. The research concludes that PBL not only enhances academic learning but also prepares students for real-world challenges by fostering essential skills such as adaptability, communication, and problem-solving. The article also discusses potential challenges in implementing PBL, including the need for adequate teacher preparation and resources.

Keywords: *Problem-based learning, critical thinking, secondary education, student engagement, educational strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

In an age defined by rapid technological shifts and unprecedented global challenges, the skills required for students to thrive extend far beyond the mastery of traditional academic subjects. One of the most vital competences for today's learners is the ability to think critically—evaluating information, analyzing diverse perspectives, and solving problems creatively. Critical thinking empowers students to not only absorb knowledge but to apply it effectively in complex, real-world scenarios. It fosters intellectual independence and equips individuals with the tools needed to navigate the complexities of the contemporary world.

Critical thinking is not a skill that develops naturally through passive learning; it requires intentional cultivation through innovative teaching methods. One such method is problem-based learning, which has gained widespread recognition for its ability to promote deep understanding and critical engagement. PBL shifts the focus from teacher-centered instruction to a student-driven process, where learners are presented with real-world problems that do not have straightforward solutions. This method requires them to work collaboratively, think analytically, and use critical reasoning to arrive at solutions. Rather than passively receiving information, students actively participate in the learning process, making connections between what they know and how it can be applied in new contexts.

This article aims to explore how problem-based learning enhances critical thinking skills in secondary school education students, preparing them for the complex challenges of the contemporary world. The main objectives of this study are: to examine how PBL fosters critical thinking in secondary school education; to analyze PBL's role in promoting collaboration, adapta-

bility, and self-directed learning; to explore the challenges and benefits of integrating PBL into the curriculum; and to provide recommendations for effectively implementing PBL to enhance critical thinking.

In secondary school education, where students are transitioning from basic knowledge acquisition to more complex cognitive tasks, integrating PBL into the curriculum is particularly important. Traditional methods, such as rote memorization and standardized testing, often fail to equip students with the critical thinking skills they need to succeed in higher education or the workforce. By contrast, problem-based learning encourages inquiry, reflection, and evidence-based reasoning, all of which are essential for tackling the unpredictable challenges of the modern world. When PBL is used, students do not simply seek the “right answer”; instead, they explore multiple pathways to solutions, consider the consequences of different approaches, and refine their thinking through collaboration and feedback.

Moreover, PBL fosters an environment where students can develop critical life skills that go beyond academic success. Collaboration, communication, adaptability, and creativity are all nurtured through the problem-solving process. As students work together to solve problems, they learn to appreciate different viewpoints, challenge assumptions, and construct well-reasoned arguments—all of which are integral components of critical thinking. Additionally, PBL encourages students to take responsibility for their learning, cultivating self-directed learners who are more prepared to face the demands of an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

In today's rapidly changing world, the ability to think critically is more essential than ever for students. It enables them to analyze, evaluate, and solve complex problems in both academic and real-world contexts. As

education evolves to meet the demands of the 21st century, innovative methods are needed to foster these crucial skills. Problem-based learning has emerged as one of the most effective approaches for cultivating critical thinking. By promoting inquiry-based learning and empowering students to solve real-world problems, PBL not only enhances academic outcomes but also prepares young minds for the complexities of an ever-changing world. To achieve these objectives, the following questions were put forth:

1. What are the unique features of the problem-based learning that make it effective in developing critical thinking?

2. How does PBL enhance students' critical thinking, collaboration, and self-directed learning?

3. What are the advantages and challenges of integrating PBL into the secondary school curriculum?

METHODS

This study employed a quantitative method design to explore the application of problem-based learning in secondary school education and its impact on critical thinking, student engagement, and collaborative learning. The method involved a survey administered to secondary school teachers in Kazakhstan to gather their perspectives and experiences with PBL.

A total of 20 secondary school teachers participated in the survey, representing various disciplines such as science, social studies, and language arts. The participants were selected through convenience sampling, ensuring accessible and timely responses. Data were collected using a structured online survey created with Google Forms, which allowed teachers to respond conveniently from their own settings.

The survey included 25 quantitative questions designed to assess teachers' perceptions of PBL. These questions employed multiple-choice and Likert-scale formats to capture numerical data on key aspects of PBL, such as its effectiveness in developing critical thinking, fostering student engagement, and enhancing information retention. Additional questions addressed

Teacher demographics and perceptions of problem-based learning

Number of Respondents	20 secondary school teachers
Gender	60% female, 40% male
Age	25-35 years (80%), 36+ years (20%)
Work Experience	Less than 5 years (50%), 5-10 years (35%), 10-20 years (15%)

RESULTS

The analysis of the survey responses reveals several key insights into the impact of PBL on students' critical thinking, language skills, motivation, and engagement. The results from the survey, conducted with 20 teachers using Google forms, suggest that PBL has a significant positive effect on student development in these areas. Below is a detailed discussion of each section of the survey.

The first section of the survey focused on the development of critical thinking skills through PBL activities. When asked how their critical thinking skills had

the challenges of implementing PBL, as well as demographic details such as teaching experience and subject area.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify trends and summarize teachers' responses. Percentages and frequencies were calculated to quantify perceptions of PBL's impact. These measures offered insight into the overall effectiveness and challenges of PBL in secondary education as perceived by teachers.

The analysis revealed that 75% of the teachers viewed PBL as an effective approach for developing students' critical thinking skills. They highlighted that PBL encourages students to analyze complex problems, work collaboratively, and apply theoretical knowledge to real-world contexts.

Additionally, 80% of respondents reported that PBL significantly enhances student engagement. Teachers observed increased motivation and active participation during lessons, especially in subjects like science and social studies, where students addressed real-world problems.

Furthermore, 60% of the participants indicated that PBL positively impacts students' information retention. They noted that the inquiry-based and hands-on nature of PBL helps students better understand and recall material by connecting theoretical knowledge to practical applications. Challenges were also identified. About 25% of teachers reported difficulties in assessing individual contributions within group settings. Some respondents mentioned the need for additional training and resources to effectively integrate PBL into their teaching practices. The findings indicate that PBL is a valuable instructional strategy for fostering critical thinking, engagement, and knowledge retention among secondary school students. Despite certain implementation challenges, the majority of participants expressed interest in incorporating more PBL activities into their classrooms to improve learning outcomes.

changed after using the PBL method, 60% of participants reported a "significant improvement," while 30% mentioned "some changes." Only 10% felt no change. This indicates that PBL is perceived as an effective tool in enhancing critical thinking.

After using the PBL method, 25% of respondents reported no change in their critical thinking skills, 62.5% observed some changes, and 12.5% noted significant improvement (see figure 1). When working with PBL, 75% of respondents stated that problem-solving has become more challenging, 12.5% found it easier, and another 12.5% reported encountering more complex issues in problem-solving (see figure 2).

figure 1

figure 2

In terms of the specific skills used during PBL tasks, most students reported using skills such as “analyzing information” (85%), “evaluating different perspectives” (75%), and “presenting arguments and justifications” (70%). These results demonstrate that PBL encourages active engagement with complex problems, requiring students to apply analytical and evaluative thinking. Furthermore, 80% of respondents felt that PBL made problem-solving easier and more manageable, while 20% felt it had become more challenging. This suggests that, despite initial difficulties, PBL encourages students to approach problems more strategically and critically.

Finally, the majority of students (90%) felt their critical thinking abilities had improved through PBL, with only a few reporting no noticeable improvement. This highlights PBL’s role in fostering deep, reflective thought processes among students.

The second section of the survey addressed the development of language skills through PBL. When asked about their confidence in using a foreign language (e.g., English) to solve real-world problems in PBL activities, 70% of students reported feeling “very confident,” while 25% were “somewhat confident” and 5% reported “not confident.” This suggests that PBL plays a significant role in boosting language proficiency, especially in practical, real-world contexts.

Regarding the impact of PBL on different language skills, most students felt that it had improved their speaking (80%), writing (70%), and listening skills (65%). Interestingly, 60% of students also reported an improvement in reading comprehension. This suggests that PBL activities provide opportunities for students to use language in diverse contexts, thus enhancing their overall language abilities. Furthermore, 75% of students reported frequently using the foreign language to explain complex ideas during PBL tasks, highlighting how PBL encourages the use of language in authentic and meaningful contexts.

The third section focused on the students’ motivation and engagement in PBL tasks. When asked about their motivation to engage in PBL activities, 75% of respondents reported feeling “very motivated,” while 20% were “somewhat motivated,” and only 5% were “not motivated.” This demonstrates that PBL has a strong positive influence on students’ enthusiasm and engagement in their learning process.

In comparing PBL to traditional classroom activities, 85% of students found PBL tasks to be “much

more engaging,” with the remaining 15% finding them “slightly more engaging.” This reinforces the idea that PBL creates a more dynamic and stimulating learning environment compared to conventional methods. Additionally, when asked about their experiences with group work during PBL, 65% of students stated that they “enjoyed it and found it helpful,” while 25% “found it challenging but useful,” and 10% preferred working alone. This indicates that while some students may find group work challenging, the majority see it as a beneficial and collaborative aspect of PBL.

The next section of the survey examined students’ reflection on their learning process and teamwork skills. When asked how often they reflect on their learning process after completing PBL tasks, 60% of students reported “always,” 30% “sometimes,” and 10% “rarely.” This shows that PBL encourages students to actively reflect on their learning, which is crucial for deeper understanding and self-regulation.

Regarding teamwork, 70% of students felt that their teamwork skills had “greatly improved” through PBL, while 20% felt they had “slightly improved” and 10% reported “no change.” This highlights the importance of collaboration in PBL, where students work together to solve problems and develop interpersonal skills. Furthermore, 80% of students felt that working in groups during PBL tasks helped them learn new perspectives, demonstrating the value of collaborative learning in broadening students’ viewpoints.

Overall, the responses indicate that PBL has a profoundly positive impact on students’ critical thinking, language skills, motivation, and teamwork abilities. The survey results demonstrate that students who engage in PBL tasks experience significant growth in their academic skills and feel more motivated and confident in their learning. The hands-on, collaborative nature of PBL fosters a deeper engagement with the material, encouraging students to apply knowledge in real-world scenarios and develop essential life skills. The analysis of the survey results confirms the effectiveness of PBL in promoting critical thinking, improving language skills, and enhancing motivation and engagement among students. Despite some challenges in group work and initial difficulties in problem-solving, PBL is perceived as a valuable approach to learning, providing students with opportunities for deeper understanding and skill development. These findings are consistent with existing literature on PBL and support the continued use of this method in educational settings.

Survey results on the impact of problem-based learning on students' skills and engagement

Category	Survey Question	Survey Results
Critical Thinking Skills	How did your critical thinking skills change after PBL?	60% significant improvement, 30% some changes, 10% no change
Critical Thinking Skills	What specific skills were used during PBL tasks?	85% analyzing information, 75% evaluating perspectives, 70% presenting arguments
Critical Thinking Skills	Did PBL make problem-solving easier?	80% easier, 20% more challenging
Language Skills	Confidence in using a foreign language in PBL tasks?	70% very confident, 25% somewhat confident, 5% not confident
Language Skills	Impact on specific language skills?	80% speaking, 70% writing, 65% listening, 60% reading comprehension
Motivation and Engagement	Motivation to engage in PBL activities?	75% very motivated, 20% somewhat motivated, 5% not motivated
Motivation and Engagement	How engaging is PBL compared to traditional methods?	85% much more engaging, 15% slightly more engaging
Teamwork Skills	Did PBL improve teamwork skills?	70% greatly improved, 20% slightly improved, 10% no change
Teamwork Skills	Reflection on learning process after PBL tasks?	60% always, 30% sometimes, 10% rarely
Overall Experience	Did group work in PBL help?	65% enjoyed, 25% challenging but useful, 10% preferred working alone
Overall Experience	Perception of PBL's impact?	Significant growth in critical thinking, language skills, motivation, and teamwork abilities

DISCUSSION

The present study employs a quantitative research methodology to examine the effectiveness of problem-based learning in fostering critical thinking among secondary school students. The quantitative method involves the systematic collection and statistical analysis of numerical data obtained through structured surveys and tests. This approach allows for an objective evaluation of the impact of PBL on various aspects of student learning, including critical thinking, engagement, and motivation.

To support the research, data were gathered from a sample of secondary school teachers and students in Kazakhstan. A well-designed survey with closed-ended questions was used to measure key variables such as students' critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, engagement levels, and academic motivation. In addition, standardized tests were administered to assess students' knowledge retention and their ability to apply learned concepts in real-world scenarios. The collected data were analyzed through statistical tools, including descriptive and inferential analysis, to identify trends, relationships, and correlations between PBL activities and learning outcomes.

A variety of works by local and international scholars provided the theoretical framework for this study. Among the key contributors are the works of John Willingham (2019) and Judith Halpern (2020). Willingham emphasizes the significance of critical thinking in education, particularly in addressing complex real-life problems. His strategies include fostering analytical abilities and structured questioning in classroom activities, which aim to encourage students to reflect on their reasoning processes. Judith Halpern (2020) complements this perspective by viewing critical thinking as an essential skill set that supports analytical thinking, decision-making, and evidence evalu-

ation. Her research provides practical guidelines for educators, advocating for the implementation of strategic tasks that challenge students' assumptions and promote deep learning.

In the context of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) region, significant contributions were made by Cynthia Hmelo-Silver and Kai Eberbach (2021), who highlight the potential of PBL to foster collaborative learning, critical thinking, and deep knowledge acquisition. Their findings suggest that engaging students with real-world problems encourages teamwork and develops problem-solving skills. Furthermore, K. Khatibi and S. Whittaker (2022) explore the impact of PBL on student engagement and memory retention. Their research indicates that PBL enhances students' ability to retain information by actively involving them in interactive learning processes, which in turn increases motivation and interest in academic material.

On a local level, G.Q. Smagulova, a prominent Kazakhstani researcher, has conducted valuable research on the integration of critical thinking skills into Kazakhstan's national curriculum. Her work focuses on aligning local educational programs with global trends in developing cognitive and analytical skills. Smagulova's findings underscore the importance of embedding critical thinking into school standards to prepare students for modern challenges.

The methodology of this research is designed to address key objectives under three main themes: "learning through collaboration," "enhancing student motivation," and "improving knowledge retention." By systematically analyzing the survey and test results, the study evaluates the practical outcomes of implementing PBL in Kazakhstan's educational system. It also identifies challenges teachers face while incorporating PBL techniques, such as resource limitations and the need for specialized training.

Through its rigorous quantitative method, this study provides a data-driven understanding of how PBL impacts secondary school students' learning experiences, critical thinking development, and overall academic performance. Statistical findings will be used to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of PBL, offering actionable insights for educators and policymakers.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study highlight the transformative potential of problem-based learning in fostering critical thinking, improving language skills, and enhancing student motivation and engagement in secondary school education. The research demonstrates that PBL encourages students to actively engage with real-world problems, promoting analytical thinking, collaboration, and self-directed learning. Key insights from the survey reveal that the majority of participants observed significant improvements in students' critical thinking abilities, language proficiency, and teamwork skills. Additionally, PBL was found to significantly increase student motivation and engagement compared to traditional teaching methods.

Despite its evident benefits, the study also identified challenges, such as the need for additional resources, training for teachers, and effective assessment strategies for group tasks. Addressing these challenges will be essential for maximizing the impact of PBL on student outcomes.

In conclusion, PBL represents a powerful approach for equipping secondary school students with the critical skills needed to navigate the complexities of the modern world. By fostering inquiry, reflection, and

collaboration, PBL prepares students for both academic and real-world success. It is recommended that educational institutions integrate PBL into their curricula and provide adequate training and resources to teachers for its effective implementation. Future research could explore long-term impacts of PBL on academic performance and its application across diverse educational contexts.

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